

Outer alchemy (外丹, waidan)

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Outer Alchemy (外丹, waidan), corresponding to Inner alchemy (内丹, Neidan), is a Daoist doctrine and methodology focused on cultivating personal morality and compounding elixirs (jin/golden cinnabar) from minerals, metals, and herbs for the sake of conferring longevity and immortality. Outer alchemy is based on Laozi's "Dao" philosophy, adding Zhuangzi's transcendental thought and Zhang Daoling's mystical theory, and advocates practitioners to cultivate immortality (修仙, xiuxian) by training Confucian ethics, valuing the dao (道), refining and ingesting elixir. In practitioners' faith, elixirs can activate and nourish qi (氣, energy), thereby vitalizing the people's physical health and attain mental transcendence. Outer alchemy had been mentioned during the Western Han Dynasty (202 BC – 9 AD) by esoterica masters (方士, fangshi) and written in Yantie lun (《鹽鐵論》, Discourses on Salt and Iron, ca. 60 BCE.), Hongbao yuanbi shu (《鴻寶苑祕術》, Arts from the Garden of Secrets of the Vast Treasure), Hanshu (《漢書》), many Taiqing 太清 Daoism text, especially in Ge Hong's Baopuzi (《抱朴子》, He Who Holds to Simplicity). Outer alchemy developed mostly during the Tang Dynasty, however, the abuse of elixirs led to unexpected deaths of Emperor Wuzong (r. 840–46), Xuanzong (r. 846–59), and possibly also Xianzong (r. 805–20). From the late Tang onward, outer alchemy gradually declined. Ge Hong (also Ko Hung 葛洪, 283–343 CE, Danyang, Jiangsu) is one the most well-known Waidan masters. His main text, Baopuzi, consists of Neipian (内篇, "20 Inner Chapters", focusing on alchemical studies and the pursuit of immortality) and Waipian (外篇, "50 Outer Chapters", stressing the importance of Confucian ethic cultivation of the secular lives). Against the background of the long period of chaos (220–589 CE), Ge Hong founded esoteric studies, immortality cultivation and outer alchemy based on the natural principle of "metamorphoses" (變化, bianhua). Ge considered this profane world is not "closed, final, and perpetual reality"; instead, it is "infinite, boundless, and endless world of new things" that only transcended immortals (xian, 仙) could access. Transcended immortals, in Ge's thought, are "non-aging, non-dying" beings who are living in the fairy world of eternal happiness. A man must maintain his purity (especially the Confucian concept of benevolence (仁ren)) before cultivating immortality. Ge concluded that dao is the "root" and ru is the "branch." Based on Ge Hong's concepts, outer alchemy became popular in ancient China.

Date Range: 200 BCE - 900 CE

Region: Han

Region tags: East Asia, Asia, China

Han

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Pregadio, Fabrizio. "Elixirs and alchemy." *Taoism Handbook*, ed. Livia Kohn, pp. 165-195. Leiden, Boston & Koln: Brill. 2000.

- Source 2: Pregadio, Fabrizio. "Ge Hong" & "Waidan." *The Encyclopedia of Taoism*, London & New York: Routledge, 2008, 442-3; 1002-4.
- Source 3: Lai Chi-Tim. "Ko Hung's Discourse of Hsien-Immortality: A Daoist Configuration of an Alternate Ideal Self-Identity." *Numen* 45 (1998): 183-220.
- Source 1: Ware, James R. *Alchemy, Medicine & Religion in the China of A.D. 320: The Nei P'ien of Ko Hung*. Rpt.; New York: Dover Publications, Inc., 1981
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- Source 3: Yang Mingzhao 楊明照 ed., *Baopuzi waipian jiaojian 抱朴子外篇校箋*, Beijing : Zhonghua shu ju: Xin hua shu dian Beijing fa xing suo fa xing (新編諸子集成. 第一輯/Xin bian zhu zi ji cheng) 2:30.65.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: "Outer Alchemy" and "Inner Alchemy" within the Chinese Tradition of Taoism. Website: <https://zinaidastoenescu.com/outer-alchemy-and-inner-alchemy-within-the-chinese-tradition-of-taoism/>
- Source 1 Description: Description and generalization of Chinese Neidan and Waidan in Chinese Daoist tradition.
- Source 2 URL: "Alchemy", Encyclopedia of world problem and human potential, website: <http://encyclopedia.uia.org/en/development/11858870>
- Source 2 Description: Definition and short description on Waidan
- Source 3 URL: "Alchemy", Scholarly Community Encyclopedia, website: <https://encyclopedia.pub/entry/34860>
- Source 3 Description: General description of both Neidan and Waidan alchemy

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: Ge Hong (1958), *Baopuzi [Nei pian 20 juan, Wai pian 50 juan] (抱朴子。內篇20卷, 外篇50卷)*, Taipei: Shi jie shu ju / (世界文庫. 四部刊要). 1958.
- Source 1 Description: Original text written by Ge Hong, the most influential master of Outer Alchemy in Chinese Daoist history.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: The outer alchemy corresponds to the inner alchemy, and together they shaped Daoism in ancient China. Both are based on Laozi's view of "Dao" and the mystical transcendental theories of Zhuangzi and Zhang Daoling. Inner alchemists advocate both physical and heart-mind self-cultivation in order to achieve the goal of immortality; while outer alchemists pursue physical health, moral cultivation, and refine and ingest elixirs to achieve the same goal. Indirectly, Outer alchemy is consistent with Confucianism in terms of moral cultivation, and corresponds to Buddhism in terms of the cause-and-effect principle of moral education.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: Outer alchemy corresponds and is somehow competitive with Inner alchemy and other related Daoist school in ancient China.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: The Outer Alchemy (Waidan) corresponds to the Inner Alchemy (Neidan), both facilitate the rise of Daoism in Chinese history during the Han and Tang dynasties.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: With exception of the Taiqing Daoism which adopted outer alchemy as one of their core religious practice, Outer Alchemy, in general, did not have a complete system of criteria for assigning its affiliation.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: Research on Ge Hong, the most influential master of outer alchemy, tells us a fact: the Han Dynasty did not attack outer alchemy. Ge Hong received support from local authorities while in Guangzhou (Guangdong Province), where he practiced Waidan, formulated herbal medicines, and wrote his famous book Baopuzi 抱朴子. Ge Hong in his philosophy integrated both Confucian ethics (in Baopuzi's Waipian) and Daoist "dao" (in Baopuzi's Neipian). Later generations of outer alchemists were more concerned with religious activities in their religious institutions far away from society. Initially, due to a sense of isolation, Waidan had almost no contact with the state or local authorities. During the Tang Dynasty, both the Waidan sect and the Neidan sect adhered to court laws in order to pursue orthodoxy; however, the core concepts and operating principles of their religious groups remained outside the scope of state concern.

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– No

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– No

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– No

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

Notes: Although outer alchemists also focused on Confucian moral cultivation, their religious codes were completely different from the imperial laws.

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Compared with inner alchemy, outer alchemy operated mainly on a personal scale, so there was a vague distinction between those who adhered to principles and those who broke them.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no clear written record of the number of outer alchemists during the Han and Tang dynasties.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Outer alchemy was inherited by specific disciples of the same tradition, including the Taiqing Daoist sect. There are no records showing the number of adherents throughout the ages.

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– No

Notes: Outer alchemy is a theory and methodology of self-cultivation, so it has no recognized leader throughout the ages, except for the fact that practitioners used to worship Laozi (Tai Shang Laojun) and other Taoist/Daoist masters.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: All classics were written in Han Chinese scripture.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Outer alchemy Daoist temples (shrines) used to have small or medium-sized buildings/complexes, but all of them have collapsed.

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: All the outer alchemist temples built during the Han and Tang Dynasties collapsed, and the new buildings/structures cannot reflect the precise model and size of the ancient monuments.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Today, the original monument no longer exists.

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– On persons

– Only religious public space

Notes: There are specific Daoist images on Daoist temples (statues, buildings, paintings, etc.) and on the clothing of alchemists.

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– No

Notes: The formal "Daoist temple (道館 Daoguan)" has been a centralized place for alchemists to stay and conduct religious activities in the ancient times. Many other alchemists chose to stay at their private home. Today, among some special sites, statues, paintings and/or cultural images related to iconic figures such as Laozi, Zhang Daoling, Ge Hong, Tao Hongjing, etc. have been preserved or reconstructed as sacred relics/historical relics.

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: Once outer alchemists become immortal, they can transform, be beautiful, be happy and powerful forever

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: Outer alchemists believed that once they became immortals, they could have a fairyland life that transcended the material world.

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– Yes [specify]: External alchemists believed that the living human body is the prerequisite entity for the entire process of cultivating immortality. The physical body requires health while the heart-mind needs moral cultivation. When one meets all the conditions and takes the elixir, he can transform from the mortal world into an immortal and live in the fairy world or heaven. After death, the body is just the remaining material part, which will then decompose, and only the spirit can live in its world forever.

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: In ancient times, outer alchemists believed that by cultivating one's morality and taking elixirs, one could achieve transcendence and become an immortal. Immortals are supposed to live in fairyland in the Heaven, on mountains or on holy islands offshore.

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Notes: Once one becomes an immortal, he/she will live in Heaven or a fairyland (仙境,

xianjing), which is vaguely described as being on the sky, on sacred mountains or on holly islands

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:
– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:
– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:
– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:
– Yes [specify]: Heaven, sacred mountains, sacred islands, etc.

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: Alchemists sought to transform into immortality and live in the fairy world instead of being reincarnated back into this profane world.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Early masters such as Laozi and Zhuangzi were told that they "integrated their bodies with nature" or their remains were unknown, while later generations of outer alchemists, such as Ge Hong, were mainly buried in collective or family graveyards.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Field doesn't know

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: In the Daoist tradition, especially in Ge Hong's "The Legends of Immortals/Shenxianzhuan", Daoist priests who practiced well could become immortals. In addition, there are various gods that are transcended from nature (trees, animals, mountains, rivers, oceans, winds, clouds, etc.) or gods/fairies borrowed from Buddhism and folk religions.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: In Daoist pantheon, the highest god is the Jade Emperor of Heaven who is supported by great Daoist god Tai Shang Laojun (transcended Laozi) and other immortals.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: Daoists believe that the highest god is the Jade Emperor of Heaven. He actually resembles the Chinese emperor in the secular world.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: The Jade Emperor in heaven rules the heavenly world and governs the profane world.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– Yes

Notes: In the Daoist tradition, the Heavenly Court is similar to the model of the Chinese monarchy, with similar norms and principles.

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: He is the ruler of the Heaven, the world, and the underworld

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: He is the master god of all gods and fairies, his knowledge is believed not to be restricted.

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can punish:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
 - Field doesn't know
 - Notes: The Jade Emperor, with the support of heavenly officials and immortals, rewards or punishes people based on their merits and moral cultivation.
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - No
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– No

Notes: In Daoist beliefs, the orders of the Jade Emperor are carried out and implemented only by heavenly officials or immortals.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: Daoist, including outer alchemists, established an immortal pantheon, and masters from past generations served as immortals of different levels. Among them, Taishang Laojun, the transcendent Laozi, is the highest.

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Daoist alchemists who have successfully cultivated Waidan can be transformed into immortals; some adepts or ordinary people believe that they can see immortals in their dreams. Folk religions closely integrated with Taoism also have similar beliefs.

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: Immortals are believed to be knowledgeable beyond the profane world.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

Notes: Due to cultural diffusion/incorporation between Daoism, Confucianism, Buddhism, and Chinese folk religions, many popular people also believe in immortals.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
– Yes

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
– Yes

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
– Yes

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):
– Yes

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
– Yes

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:
– Yes [specify]: People believe that immortals perform the task of cause-effect judgment in human life on behalf of the Jade Emperor of Heaven.

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

Notes: Daoism itself advocates moral cultivation based on the principle of cause and effect. In addition, when Taoism was integrated with Confucianism and Buddhism, this causal relationship was closely related to secular society.

↳ Human spirits can reward:
– Yes

↳ Human spirits can punish:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:
– Field doesn't know

Notes: In the faith of alchemists, immortals who have achieved transcendence and

immortality will not bring about worldly affairs and memories. Instead, they started a new carefree life in the fairy world.

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: The transcendent immortals are ordered by the Jade Emperor of Heaven to return to the earthly world to observe and carry out the task of the law of cause, or to guide moral people in dreams to overcome their troubles..

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– No

↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: being transformable in physical appearance; performing various tasks assigned by the Jade Emperor in Heaven; being able to exorcise demons.

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination processes:

– Yes

↳ Only through specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: In people's dreams or being told in stories, both human and non-human immortals sometime "appear" to take care of the law of cause and effect or to guide moral people in specific worldly affairs.

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

Notes: Some stories show that sacred figures such as the monkey god (in "the Journey to the West") and the dragon were sometimes "hungry," but these facts have more to do with folk religions than with Daoism itself.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Some legends indicate that beasts and animals such as blue and white snakes and wild foxes can "cultivate" to be immortals, but these facts have more to do with folk religion than with Daoism itself.

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– Yes [specify]: In Daoism and folk belief, the Jade Emperor, fairies, and immortals are organized into a heavenly royal court, simulating China's model of monarchy in this world.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: Immortals "supervise" the profane world under the order of the Jade Emperor of Heaven.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Immortals care about the moral cultivation of all mankind. They oversee the cultivation of prevailing social norms (probably Confucian ethics), the laws of cause and effect, and "guide" virtuous people toward better lives.

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– Yes

Notes: In Daoist beliefs, non-violence/non-killing is applied. Vegetarianism is encouraged.

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Notes: Adepts and followers are instructed to pay homage to past masters, immortals, sacred figures, sacred temples/shrines, and iconic symbols.

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Notes: Alchemy attaches great importance to various sacred objects, such as elixirs, alchemy furnaces, Yin and Yang Bagua, Daoist flags, etc.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Immortals are responsible for ensuring the circulation of the "Dao" (the law of nature and all beings)

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
 - Field doesn't know
 - Notes: Immortals are sex-free, but there are not enough clues to substantiate their concerns about human sexuality.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:
 - Yes
 - Notes: In outer/inner alchemy Daoism, honesty and truthfulness are two of the most important moral values (see Ge Hong's Outer Chapters).

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Alchemists must perform oath-taking ceremonies and regularly offer sacrifices to gods. The gods were told to be overseers of these oaths and to reward those who kept them.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:
 - Yes
 - Notes: The diligence of ordinary people is highly appreciated by alchemists; therefore, they believe that immortals are always around these diligent people and punish those who are lazy.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
 - Yes
 - Notes: People believe that immortals have sorcery. They intervene in the secular world through magic.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
 - Yes
 - Notes: In Daoist belief, immortals appear in dreams and guide virtuous people to avoid risks and overcome the troubles in life.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Alchemists pay attention to Confucian ethical cultivation, so they also pay attention to

filial piety and respect for the elderly. They believe that those who fail to do so will be punished by immortals.

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Notes: In the beliefs of the alchemists, morality was a prerequisite for living a good secular life and/or cultivating immortality, so they oversaw the law of cause and effect. Criminal behavior was strictly prohibited.

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: In the faith of the alchemists, immortals observed them practicing regular rituals, moral cultivation, and immortality cultivation.

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: Alchemists must have paid regular rituals as to show their loyalty to the "Dao" and immortals.

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Although there are not enough clues to confirm, the alchemists once carried out some activities that affected ordinary people and attracted their attention and participation. While practicing outer alchemy, Ge Hong composed herbal medicines to provide herbal treatments for ordinary people on Mt. Luofu in Guangzhou Prefecture (the present-day Guangdong province).

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

Notes: According to the beliefs of all alchemists, immortal cultivators must maintain personal hygiene.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: The immortals are said to take care of the moral life of human families and

societies. They may support the virtuous and punish those who violate norms.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Immortals are banned from falling in love with the others; those who fail to comply with this "heavenly regulation" will be punished by the Jade Emperor of Heaven.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– Yes

Notes: Those who practice moral cultivation and outer alchemy would have opportunities to become immortals

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

Notes: Many Chinese legends (based on political narratives) indicate that immortals sometimes "appear" to support armed forces in defeating their enemies in battle.

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - Field doesn't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Outer alchemists, especially Ge Hong, believed that only people with good moral cultivation could ingest elixirs to become immortals.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present and clear

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– Yes

Notes: In outer Alchemy, Confucian ethics are highlighted, clearly written in Ge Hong's Baopuzi Waipian (Outer Chapters of Baopuzi), including 50 chapters stressing the importance of Confucian principles of the secular lives. In Ge Hong's point of view, Confucianism guides people to deal with the secular world and establish a moral social life, while esoteric Daoism releases people's inner world and provides ways to obtain immortality.

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

Notes: Outer alchemists believe that before transcending immortality, one must live a moral secular life; an immortal is a symbol of a person who has practiced well, both morally and in cultivating immortality.

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– No

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– All individuals within society

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– No

↳ Courage (generic):

– No

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

Notes: Benevolence was specially highlighted by Ge Hong and other outer alchemists.

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Cooperation:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Moderation / frugality:
– Yes

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
– Yes

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Strength (physical):
– Yes

Notes: In the process of cultivating immortality, outer alchemists hope to nourish the physical body by taking elixirs and achieve immortality.

↳ Power / status / nobility:
– No

↳ Humility / modesty:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
– Yes

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Optimism / hope:
 - Yes
- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Wisdom / understanding:
 - Yes
- ↳ Discernment / intelligence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Beauty / attractiveness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:
 - No

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: Outer alchemy requires prohibition of sexual behavior during the process of cultivating immortality.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: Alchemists must cultivate virtue.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Yes

Notes: Cultivation of immortality requires staying away from the secular world.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A band

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: Alchemists used the generic Han Chinese scripture in their classics and other religious texts. There was no distinct written language applied.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Notes: They followed the imperial calendar (Chinese lunar calendar).

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The dynasties.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

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